

Effect Of Board Of Director Attributes On Financial Statement Fraud Of Listed Consumer Good Companies In Nigeria

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Abstract

This study evaluates the effect of board of director attributes on financial statement fraud of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria for the period 2014 - 2023. An ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of twenty one (21) consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Limited (NGX). This study utilized purposive sampling technique to arrive at fifteen (15) sample consumer goods companies for this study. The data used in this study were secondary derived from the annual reports and accounts of consumer goods companies that are listed on the NGX. The study used logistic regression to analyse data. The logistic regression result revealed that board independence and board gender diversity have a significant effect on financial statement fraud. While, corporate culture has no significant influence on financial statement fraud of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The study concludes that board independence and board gender diversity reduce the odds of financial statement fraud occurring. Corporate culture has no influence on financial statement fraud. The study recommends that consumer goods companies' management in Nigeria should implement robust governance practices including internal audits, independent audit committees, and transparent decision-making to monitor financial practices and mitigate fraud risks. Additionally, fostering ethical conduct, transparency, and integrating board gender diversity initiatives can promote integrity, compliance, and inclusive leadership in these organizations.

Keywords: Board attributes, Board independence, Corporate culture, Board gender diversity, Financial statement fraud

Word count:

1.1 Introduction

Financial statement fraud is a significant issue that affects economies worldwide. The global financial landscape has witnessed numerous corporate scandals resulting from fraudulent financial reporting. These scandals in the past include Enron and WorldCom which have caused massive financial losses and eroded investor confidence, prompting regulatory bodies to enhance corporate governance frameworks (Umar-Dauda & Oyedokun, 2018; Afes & Jarbou, 2023). Despite these measures, financial statement fraud persists, highlighting inherent weaknesses in corporate

oversight and accountability mechanisms. The International Federation of Accountants (IFAC) emphasizes that effective corporate governance is crucial in preventing financial fraud, yet many organizations still struggle to implement these practices effectively (Oyedokun, 2019; IFAC, 2022).

In developing economies like Nigeria, the issue of financial statement fraud is exacerbated by a combination of factors including weak regulatory enforcement, inadequate governance practices, and a lack of transparency. Notable cases in the past such as the Cadbury Nigeria, Heritage bank, Oceanic, Intercontinental bank plc scandal had illustrated the severe consequences of fraudulent financial reporting on both financial stability and corporate reputation. These incidents underscore systemic issues within Nigerian corporate governance structures, significantly impacting investor confidence and the overall business environment. Strengthening governance frameworks and ensuring rigorous enforcement are essential to address these challenges in Nigeria. Board governance attributes are among such essentials (Oyedokun, & Nwaokolobia, & Andah, 2019).

Board attributes refer to the characteristics and composition of a corporate board of directors. These include board independence, gender diversity (including gender and expertise), size, and the mix of executive and non-executive directors. Attributes like independence ensure unbiased oversight, diversity brings varied perspectives, and the right expertise enhances decision-making capabilities, collectively influencing governance effectiveness and organizational performance. However, this study restricts itself to board independent, corporate culture and board gender diversity as board attributes.

Board independence is another essential attribute linked to reducing financial statement fraud. Independent directors are expected to provide unbiased oversight and hold management accountable, which is crucial in preventing fraudulent activities (Naburgi, Ojo, & Oyedokun, 2024; Chang, 2023). The Resource Dependence Theory posits that boards with a higher proportion of independent directors are better equipped to provide critical resources, including independent judgment and oversight, which can enhance the board's effectiveness in monitoring and controlling management behavior (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978; Oyedokun, Micah, & Gimba, 2020). Therefore, number of non-executive directors on the board can be an effective strategy in curbing financial fraud.

Corporate culture plays a pivotal role in shaping ethical behavior within organizations, influencing the likelihood of financial statement fraud occurrences. A culture that values integrity, transparency, and ethical decision-making can act as a deterrent to fraudulent activities (Achinto, et al., 2023). Conversely, a toxic culture that prioritizes short-term profits and disregards ethical norms may foster an environment conducive to financial misconduct (Li, et al., 2021).

Board gender diversity also plays a significant role in enhancing corporate governance and reducing financial statement fraud. Diverse boards are more likely to challenge management decisions and foster rigorous oversight, thereby reducing the potential for fraud (Kaituko, et al., 2023; Izevbekhai & Ohiokha, 2017). Thus, gender-diverse boards can enhance the quality of decision-making and governance, contributing to more effective fraud prevention.

This study is motivated by the need to understand how these board attributes such as board independence, corporate culture, and board gender diversity impact financial statement fraud in Nigerian consumer goods' companies. Ebaid (2023) explored the impact of board characteristics on financial statement fraud in Saudi Arabia, found that board independence significantly reduces the likelihood of fraud. Kweki (2021) reviewed literature on the same topic in Nigeria, revealing both positive and negative relationships between board independence and fraud. Anichebe et al. (2019) and Eneh (2018) found that greater board independence reduces the likelihood of financial statement fraud in Nigerian firms. Previous studies have often overlooked the synergistic effects of board independence, corporate culture, and board gender diversity on financial statement fraud prevention strategies. There is a lack of comprehensive research on how these factors interact within specific organizational contexts and regulatory environments. Furthermore, existing literature has not sufficiently explored the longitudinal impact and sustainability of these governance attributes in mitigating fraud risk over time (Erkens, et al., 2012; Oyedokun, Umoh, Haruna, & Zakari, 2019). Comparative studies across diverse industries and regions could provide deeper insights into effective governance practices tailored to different organizational settings.

There is also a paucity of research specifically addressing the combined effect of these board attributes in the context of Nigerian consumer goods companies. This study aims to fill this gap by providing a comprehensive analysis of how these attributes influence the incidence of financial statement fraud in this sector. Drawing from the main objective of examining the effects of board

of director attributes on the financial statement fraud of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria, the specifics are:

- i. Assess the effect of board independence on financial statement fraud of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria;
- ii. Examine the effect of corporate culture on financial statement fraud of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria; and
- iii. Determine the effect of board gender diversity on financial statement fraud of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

2 Literature Review

Financial Statement Fraud

Financial statement fraud is a deliberate act aimed at distorting the true financial health of a company, often involving deceptive practices like inflating revenues, understating expenses, or manipulating accounting entries. These actions are intended to mislead stakeholders, including investors, regulators, and creditors, into believing the company is more profitable and stable than it actually is (Rezaee, 2005; Dauda, Ojo, Oyedokun, & Ajayi-Owoeye, 2018). In doing so, perpetrators seek to bolster stock prices, qualify for loans under false pretenses, or trigger performance-based bonuses for executives, thereby enriching themselves at the expense of others.

The impact of financial statement fraud can be devastating and widespread. It not only results in significant financial losses for investors who rely on accurate financial information but also undermines market trust and confidence in the affected company. Moreover, the legal ramifications can be severe, leading to investigations, regulatory penalties, and civil or criminal charges against those responsible.

Detecting financial statement fraud requires robust methods and tools. The M-score, developed by Beneish (1999), is a widely recognized model that uses financial ratios and other accounting metrics to identify potential manipulation in financial statements. Beyond the M-score, other methods include forensic accounting techniques, anomaly detection algorithms, and data analytics that scrutinize patterns and inconsistencies in financial data (Yahaya, Oyedokun, & Aruwa, 2019;

Beemamol, 2024). These approaches aim to enhance the ability to detect suspicious activities early, mitigate risks, and protect stakeholders from the adverse consequences of financial statement fraud. This study adopts the M-score, developed by Beneish (1999).

Board of Directors Attributes

Board of director attributes refer to the characteristics and qualities of individuals serving on a company's board, which can significantly influence corporate governance and the overall performance of the organization. Key attributes include the board independence, corporate culture, and board gender diversity. These attributes collectively contribute to the board's ability to effectively monitor management, mitigate risks, and uphold the integrity of financial reporting (Ojo, Oyedokun, & Fodio, 2020).

Board Independence

Board independence is critical in providing unbiased oversight and reducing the likelihood of financial misreporting. Independent directors are expected to act in the best interest of shareholders and ensure transparency in financial reporting (Chang 2023; Joshi, 2022; Ajit, 2014). Previous research suggests that a higher proportion of independent directors is negatively correlated with financial statement fraud (Ebaid, 2023; Kweki, 2021). This study describes board independence as the proportion of non-executive directors on the board to the total board size.

Corporate Culture

Corporate culture comprises the shared values, norms, and behaviors that define an organization's identity and guide employee conduct. It influences decision-making processes, employee engagement, and organizational performance (Deepalakshmi, et al., 2024; Mansor, et al., 2023). Studies highlight that a strong corporate culture fosters innovation, enhances employee morale, and contributes to sustainable competitive advantage (Solomon & Aliyu, 2023; Abri, et al., 2019; Ocansey & Ganu, 2017). Moreover, corporate culture is increasingly recognized as a critical factor in attracting talent, shaping organizational resilience, and navigating challenges in dynamic business environments (Moses, 2018; Omar et al., 2015)

A strong ethical culture, emphasizing integrity and transparency, serves as a deterrent to financial statement fraud by promoting accountability and adherence to regulatory standards (Solomon & Aliyu, 2023; Abri, et al., 2019). Conversely, a toxic culture that prioritizes short-term gains over ethical conduct can foster an environment conducive to fraudulent activities, undermining trust and investor confidence (Li, et al., 2021). Therefore, corporate culture according to this study, is the collective values, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors that define how an organization operates and interacts internally and externally.

Board Gender Diversity

Board gender diversity brings diverse perspectives to corporate governance and decision-making processes. Studies have shown that gender-diverse boards are more effective in monitoring management and preventing fraudulent activities (Ebaid, 2023; Izevbekhai & Ohiokha, 2017). Gender diversity is linked to improved financial performance and ethical standards (Okoro & Nnaji, 2023; Md, et al., 2022). However, this study defined board gender diversity as the number of females on the board of directors of an organisation

Empirical Review

Board Independence and Financial Statement Fraud

Using Beneish M-Score, Ibrahim and Yahaya (2024) examined the relationship between board of directors and financial statements fraud for a sample of 155 publicly traded firms in Nigeria, over 2013-2022 period. The study utilised board independence, board size, and board gender diversity as proxies for board of directors while financial statements fraud was proxied by the Beneish M-Score. The study analysis revealed that board independence has a negative significant effect on financial statements fraud. The study failed to incorporate corporate culture into its analysis. Including such variables improves the understanding of the relationship. Furthermore, the study used 155 listed firms in the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) without taken cognizant of their peculiar sectoral differences. The various sectors are prone to different degrees of fraud occurrences.

Kaituko, et al. (2023) conducted a study on the moderating effect of audit fee on the relationship between board structure and the likelihood of financial statements fraud (LFSF). The study used

logistic regression and a sample of 15 manufacturing firms listed within the East African Community partner states from 2007 to 2021. The Beneish M-Score was used as measure of the likelihood of financial statements fraud. The findings indicated that there is a significant relationship between board independence and likelihood of financial statements fraud. The current study contributes to the effect of corporate board governance on financial statement fraud by introducing proxies such as corporate culture which provides a clearer picture than that of Kaituko et al (2023). Furthermore, the findings cannot be generalized because of differences in institutional policies and environmental factors.

Using the modified Beneish M-score model as measure for fraudulent financial statements, Ebaid (2023) explored the relationship between board characteristics and the likelihood of fraud in financial statements in the Saudi stock exchange as one of the emerging markets. Financial statements of 67 companies listed on the Saudi Stock Exchange was collected over six years from 2014 to 2019. Panel data techniques was used to examine the relationship between financial statement fraud and four characteristics of the board which are independence, size, meetings frequency, and gender diversity. The finding indicates that the likelihood of fraud in financial statements is negatively and significantly related to board independence. However, the study's exclusive focus on board independence and limited attention to the corporate culture, and gender diversity leaves gaps in understanding how these elements interact to influence fraud prevention.

Kweki (2021) did a review of extant literature on the relationship between board composition and financial statements fraud in Nigeria. Board composition was proxied by board independence, board expertise, and board diligence. Finding revealed that board independence has both positive and negative relationship between board independence and financial statements fraud in Nigeria. The study is limited to other literatures findings which may have not captured other board composition such as tone at the top level management, corporate culture, existence of independent directors and board diversity. More so, the findings from previous literatures he reviewed may not be applicable to other sectors of the economy.

Anichebe, et al. (2019) examined the nexus between financial statement fraud and corporate governance elements using panel data collected from firms under the agricultural sector of the Nigeria stock exchange between 2013 and 2017 financial year. Longitudinal design and binary

logit regression technique were employed in analyzing the data. The result revealed that financial statement fraud likelihood can be attributable to board independence in quoted agricultural companies in the Nigeria Stock Exchange. However, the exclusive focus on panel data from a single sector and limited timeframe may restrict the generalizability of findings to other industries and over longer periods, warranting caution in extrapolating conclusions.

Eneh (2018) examined the effect of board attributes on corporate fraud likelihood of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The board attributes was proxied with board size, board independence and board diversity and the beneish M-score was used as the measure of fraud likelihood. The study utilized a longitudinal research design. The sample covered 15 manufacturing companies in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) as at 2017. Secondary data were utilized for the study and the data was extracted from the annual reports of corporate organizations for the period 2012-2017 financial years. The binary regression was employed as the method of data analysis in the study. The findings revealed that the odd ratio of board independence is 0.66031 which implies that changes in managerial ownership will reduce the odds of corporate fraud.

Corporate Culture and Financial Statement Fraud

Using primary data source, Solomon and Aliyu (2023) evaluated the influence of tone at the top on financial statement fraud of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study used ethical leadership strategy, corporate ethical culture and risk management practices as the proxies of tone at the top while financial statement fraud was measured by improper revenue recognition dimension. The study adopted correlational survey design and used primary data via structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed by Pearson Product Moment Correlation and multiple linear regression model with the aid of SPSS version 25. The study found that corporate ethical culture and risk management practices positively significantly related to financial statement fraud of quoted Nigerian manufacturing companies in the period of this study. The study by Solomon and Aliyu (2023) used primary data set meanwhile this study makes use of secondary data source because it cannot be manipulated while primary data set can be manipulated and that can distort the result.

Abri, et al. (2019) analysed the impacts of corporate governance system on the financial statement frauds particularly with companies in Tanzania. The study used quantitative research which incorporates primary data. The primary data of the study was elicited through administration of questionnaire to stakeholders of the companies in Tanzania. The results indicated that corporate culture has a direct impact on the financial statement fraud. The study's reliance on primary data collection through questionnaires is a strength as it allows for direct insights from stakeholders. However, the finding is specific to Tanzanian companies and may not be applicable to companies in other countries or regions with different regulatory frameworks, cultural norms, and business environments. Therefore, the generalizability of the findings beyond Tanzania is limited.

Moses (2018) investigated the relationship between corporate culture and financial statement fraud among listed companies in Nigeria. Data for the study was collected from primary sources through the issue of structured questionnaires to the top and mid-level accounting staff of fourteen companies listed on the Nigerian stock market and analyzed using descriptive statistics and the OLS method of the multiple regression analysis. The findings showed that there is a negative relationship between corporate culture and the perpetration of financial statement fraud in listed companies. Thus, strong corporate culture in terms of teamwork and communication will lead to a reduction in financial statement fraud. The findings also indicated that there is a negative relationship between corporate culture in terms of transparency and accountability and financial statement fraud. The study by Moses (2018) relied on primary data collected via structured questionnaires which may be subject to bias. The study could be critiqued again for not examining other critical variables such as board independence, and board gender diversity, which are essential in corporate governance literature.

Ocansey and Ganu (2017) did an exploratory study to examine the role of corporate culture in managing occupational fraud. The study found that contend that corporate culture plays a critical role in managing the risks of fraudulent acts. Particularly, when ethics is solidly implanted in corporate culture and exemplified by top leadership, an organization is more likely to minimize internal scams.

Omar et al. (2015) investigated the impact of corporate culture on the occurrence of financial statement fraud. The study spanned over a period of one year and involved a diverse population of

companies across various industries. Data for the study comprised both qualitative and quantitative information sourced from interviews, surveys, and financial reports. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative analysis of cultural factors with quantitative analysis to examine the relationship between corporate culture and financial statement fraud occurrence. Their findings suggest that corporate culture significantly shapes organizational behavior, impacting the likelihood of financial statement fraud.

Board Gender Diversity and Financial Statement Fraud

Using 155 firms listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group, Ibrahim and Yahaya (2024) assessed the relationship between board of directors and financial statements fraud from the period 2013-2022. Board of directors' was proxied by board independence, board size, and board gender diversity while financial statements fraud was measured by Beneish M-Score. Data were elicited from the annual financial statement of the sampled firms. The study used GMM to analysis the data, the analysis revealed that board gender diversity has a negative significant effect on financial statements fraud. The study used the board independence, board size, and board gender diversity as proxies for board of directors while this present study includes corporate culture as proxy for corporate board attributes which the study of Ibrahim and Yahaya (2024) did not include in their study.

Ebaid (2023) examined the relationship between board characteristics and the likelihood of fraud in financial statements in the Saudi stock exchange as one of the emerging markets. Financial statements of 67 companies listed on the Saudi Stock Exchange were collected over six years from 2014 to 2019. The modified Beneish M-score model was used to measure fraudulent financial statements. Panel data techniques was used to examine the relationship between financial statement fraud and four characteristics of the board: independence, size, meetings frequency, and gender diversity. The finding indicates that the representation of women on the board has no significant relationship with the likelihood of fraud in the financial statements. The current study will include corporate culture as indicator of board attributes which the study of Ebaid (2023) did not include.

Osemwegie-Ero, et al. (2023) evaluated the relationship corporate governance characteristics and financial statement fraud in Nigerian. Board gender diversity, board financial expertise and board

audit committee are used as indicators of corporate governance characteristics and independent variable of the study while Beneish M-score was used to measure financial statement fraud. The study used secondary data extracted from the annual reports and accounts of nine (9) oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian exchange group from 2012 to 2021. Panel least square was used to analyze the data and the findings revealed that board gender diversity do not significantly affect financial statement fraud.

Kaituko, et al. (2023) examined the moderating effect of audit fee on the relationship between board structure and the likelihood of financial statements fraud (LFSF). The study used logistic regression and a sample of 15 manufacturing firms listed within the East African Community partner states from 2007 to 2021. The Beneish M-Score was used a measure of the likelihood of financial statements fraud. The study found that board gender diversity has significant influence in reducing the likelihood of financial statements fraud.

Izevbekhai and Ohiokha (2017) assessed the relationship between board composition and financial statement fraud. The study utilized a sample of seventy five (75) firms from the universe of companies quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The data were a combined property of time series and cross-sectional covering the period, 2009 to 2016, with six hundred (600) firm-year observations. The study utilises descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, pooled binary logistic regression and analysis and panel binary logistic regression analysis with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and E-view 9.0. The result of the study reveals that the relationship between female gender composition and financial statement fraud was positive though statistically insignificant, it shows that the presence of female board members is not likely to reduce financial statement frauds of the sampled companies.

Therefore, researchers suggest three theoretical models that can help identify which board of director attributes influence financial statement fraud. Thus, the board of director attributes and financial statement fraud have been a subject of explanation in the framework of: the agency theory, fraud triangle theory and stakeholder theory.

3 Methodology

This study adopted ex-post facto research design to investigate the relationships as well as the effects of board of director attributes on financial statement fraud of listed consumer good companies on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX). This design was chosen because of its effectiveness in assessing the relationships and the effects of two or more variables (that is, the dependent and independent variables). The population of this study consists of twenty one (21) listed consumer goods companies on the NGX from year 2014-2023. The study used purposive sampling techniques to arrive at fifteen (15) consumer goods companies were used as the sample. Furthermore, secondary data were elicited from the financial statements of the sampled consumer goods companies under consideration. Logistic regression with the aid of STATA version 13 was used to test the relationship between the dependent variable and regressors. This method is considered appropriate for this analysis since the dependent variable is a dummy variable (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). Beneish M-Scores were used to determine the fraud likelihood and the model stated as follow:

$$\text{Beneish M-Score} = -4.84 + 0.92 \cdot \text{DSRI} + 0.528 \cdot \text{GMI} + 0.404 \cdot \text{AQI} + 0.892 \cdot \text{SGI} + 0.115 \cdot \text{DEPI} - 0.172 \cdot \text{SGAI} + 4.679 \cdot \text{TATA} - 0.327 \cdot \text{LVGI}.$$

Where: DSRI= Days Sales in Receivables Index, GMI= Gross Margin Index (GMI), AQI= Asset Quality Index, SGI= Sales Growth Index, DEPI= Depreciation Index, SGAI= Sales General and Administrative Expenses Index, TATA= Total Accruals to Total Assets, LVGI= Leverage Index.

The fraud likelihood threshold states that if a company scored less than -2.22 (i.e. a less negative or positive number), there is the unlikelihood for fraud occurrence. However, when the computed Beneish M-Score is greater than -2.22 or tends toward a positive value (that is, 1.0 and above), the company is likely to be engaged in fraud (Eneh, 2018).

In order to estimate the relationship between board of director attributes and financial statement fraud. Financial statement fraud, which is the dependent variable, is modelled as a function of board independence, corporate culture, and board gender diversity. The following model is used to guide the study analysis:

$$\text{FSF}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{BIN}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{COC}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{BGD}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where;

<i>FSF</i>	=	<i>Financial Statement Fraud</i>
<i>BIN</i>	=	<i>Board Independence</i>
<i>COC</i>	=	<i>Corporate Culture</i>
<i>BDV</i>	=	<i>Board Diversity</i>
β_0	=	<i>Constant in the model</i>
$\beta_1 - \beta_3$	=	<i>Explanatory power of each variable</i>
ϵ	=	<i>error term</i>
<i>i</i>	=	<i>Each company represented in the model</i>
<i>t</i>	=	<i>Year covered by the study (time)</i>

Variable, Definition, Measurement and Source

Variable	Definition	Measurement	Source
FSF	Financial Statement Fraud (Dependent Variable)	Beneish M-score. An M-Score value of less than -2.22 indicates a low probability of fraudulent activity within the company, and is assigned a value of 1. Conversely, an M-Score value greater than - 2.22 suggests a higher likelihood of fraudulent activity, and is assigned a value of 0.	Anichebe, et al. (2019) and Eneh (2018)
BID	Board Independence (Independent Variable)	Proportion of non-executive directors on the board to the total board size.	Ibrahim, and Yahaya (2024) and Anichebe, et al. (2019)
COC	Corporate Culture (Independent Variable)	Measure as a dichotomous variable if the firm has a zero tolerance for fraud as a policy statement, is given 1, if otherwise 0.	Ocansey and Ganu (2017) and Omar, et al. (2015)
BGD	Board Gender Diversity (Independent Variable)	Number of female director on the board	Ibrahim, and Yahaya (2024) and Osemwegie-Ero, et al. (2023)

Source: Researcher’s compilation, 2024

4 Results and Discussions

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev	Min	Max
FSF	150	0.487	0.501	0	1
BID	150	0.760	0.293	0.5	4
COC	150	0.393	0.490	0	1
BGD	150	1.413	1.018	0	4

Source: Stata 13 Output, 2024

Table 1 shows the mean values of Financial Statement Fraud (FSF), Board Independence (BID), Corporate Culture (COC), and Board Gender Diversity (BGD) to be 0.487, 0.760, 0.393, and 1.413 respectively. The standard deviation values of FSF, BID, COC, and BGD are 0.501, 0.293, 0.490, and 1.018 respectively.

The minimum values of the variables are 0, 0.5, 0, and 0 respectively. The maximum values of the variables are 1, 4, 1, and 4 in that order. However, the study observation is 150.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	FSF	BID	COC	BGD
FSF	1.0000			
BID	0.1554	1.0000		
COC	-0.2379	-0.2485	1.0000	
BGD	-0.0154	-0.1549	0.2504	1.0000

Source: Stata 13 Output, 2024

The correlation matrix table 2 above showed the relationship values between each explanatory variables and dependent variable. Therefore, the correlation matrix result indicated that Financial Statement Fraud (FSF) has a positive association with Board Independence (BID), while Corporate Culture (COC), and Board Gender Diversity (BGD) have a negative relationship with Financial Statement Fraud (FSF). The study revealed both positive and negative association between the variables. However, the predictor variables do not exhibit any problem of collinearity.

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
BID	1.74	0.575103
COC	1.09	0.916067
BGD	1.10	0.908932
Mean VIF	1.31	

Source: Stata 13 Output, 2024

The tolerance values and the variance inflation factor are two (2) good measures of assessing multicollinearity between the independent variables in a study. The result shows that variance inflation factor were consistently smaller than ten (10) indicating complete absence of multicollinearity (Neter et ‘al; 1996; Cassey et ‘al., 1999). Also, the tolerance values were

consistently smaller than 1.00, therefore extend the fact that there is complete absence of multicollinearity between the independent variables.

Table 4: Logistic Regression Fit Statistics

Chi-square/ Sig	16.91 (0.0020)
Log-likelihood	-67.774139
Hosmer-Lemeshow Chi-square (df, Sig)	18.60 (0.0172)
Pseudo R ²	0.1109

Source: Stata 13 Output, 2024

Table 4 presents the statistics of goodness of fit of the model and the explanatory power of the model. The model is based on selected board attributes. The Chi-square statistics suggests that the sample data describe the purpose of the model. The Hosmer-Lemeshow statistics of 18.60 also reveals that the model fits well. The Pseudo R² with a value of 0.1109 is also within the acceptable limit.

Table 5: Logistic Regression Result

FSF	Odds ratio	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]
BID	1.627307	.2204024	3.60	0.000	1.247909 2.122053
COC	1.33981	.9942822	0.39	0.693	.3128675 5.737541
BGD	1.514467	.3177605	1.98	0.048	1.003838 2.284842
_cons	.0004879	.0008595	-4.33	0.000	.0000154 .0154097

Source: Stata 13 Output, 2024

Board Independence and Financial Statement Fraud

The logistic regression result shows that the odds ratio of 1.627307 for board independence which indicates that companies with strong non-executive directors on their board reduce the odds of financial statement fraud occurring by approximately 63%, compared to companies with less non-executive directors on the board, holding all other variables constant. The relationship is statistically significant, as evidenced by the p-value of **0.000**, which is below the **5% significance threshold**. This implies that companies with more non-executive directors on the board are better equipped to oversee financial practices and prevent miscount. Therefore, the study rejects the null hypothesis which states that board independence has no significant effect on financial statement

fraud of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Furthermore, this finding is in tandem with the findings of Ibrahim and Yahaya (2024), Ebaid (2023), Eneh (2018), but contradict the finding of Kaituko, et al. (2023), Anichebe, et al. (2019).

Corporate Culture and Financial Statement Fraud

Also, the logistic regression result reveals that the odds ratio of **1.33981** for corporate culture (COC) indicates that companies with strong policy for zero tolerance for fraud practices and miscount reduces the odds of financial statement fraud occurring by approximately 34%, compared to companies that have no policy on fraud practices or miscount. However, the P value is 0.693, which is above the 5% significance threshold indicates a weak and statistically insignificant relationship between corporate culture and financial statement fraud, holding all other variable constant. This suggests that changes in corporate culture as measured in this study, do not significantly influence the occurrence of financial statement fraud in consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Therefore, the study accepts the null hypothesis which states that corporate culture has no significant effect on financial statement fraud of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. However, the finding can be aligned with the findings of Abri, et al. (2019), Moses (2018) and contrary to the findings by Solomon and Aliyu (2023), and Omar et al. (2015).

Board Gender Diversity and Financial Statement Fraud

The odds ratio of 1.514467 for board gender diversity (BGD) indicates that companies with higher levels of gender diversity on the boards with experience will reduce the odds of financial statement fraud occurring by approximately 51%, compared to companies without female directors on the boards, holding all other variables constant. This result is statistically significant with the p-value of 0.048, which is below the 5% significance threshold, suggesting a very strong relationship between board gender diversity and the likelihood of financial statement fraud of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This implies that female directors on the board may enhance oversight and accountability, contributing to a lower incidence of financial misconduct. Thus, the study rejects the null hypothesis which states that board gender diversity has no significant effect on financial statement fraud of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Therefore, the logistic regression finding agrees with the findings of Kaituko, et al. (2023), Izevbekhai and Ohiokha

(2017), and did not agree with the studies of Ibrahim and Yahaya (2024), Ebaid (2023), and Osemwegie-Ero, et al. (2023).

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

From the findings, this study concludes that board independence and board gender diversity have statistically significant effect on financial statement fraud. This implies that board independence and board gender diversity can effectively mitigate financial fraud. While, corporate culture has no significant influence on financial statement fraud of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria

Based on the conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made;

- i. Consumer goods companies' management should implement regular and thorough internal audits, establishing independent audit committees of qualified experts, and ensuring transparent decision-making and financial disclosures are essential steps to monitor financial practices, enhance stakeholder trust, and mitigate the risk of fraudulent activities in private organizations.
- ii. The management of consumer goods companies should conduct regular training sessions and workshops on ethical conduct, enforce clear codes of conduct, and foster a culture of transparency and openness to empower employees to report suspicious activities without fear of retaliation, promoting integrity and compliance in private organizations.
- iii. Manager of consumer goods companies in Nigeria should ensure board gender diversity initiatives are integrated into governance reforms, actively recruit and support women in board positions, and establish mentorship programmes to empower women leaders in private organizations, enhancing strategic decision-making and inclusivity.

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